

**STRUCTURE-RELIABILITY STUDIES OF THREE-DimensionALLY
BRAIDED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

Recent progress in the characterization of the mechanical performance of three dimensionally (3-D) braided alumina fiber FP reinforced Al-Li matrix composites has been presented. 3-D braiding appears to offer potential for the fabrication of metal matrix composites with improved toughness and reliability. 3-D braided FP/Al-Li composites have demonstrated clearly superior impact tolerance and improved fracture toughness over unidirectional and $\pm 20^\circ$ angle-ply FP/Al-Li laminates while providing the same level of in-plane strength and stiffness.

INTRODUCTION

3-D braided fiber reinforced composites are among the new, advanced structural textile composites designed to respond to the ever increasing need for delamination resistance and damage tolerance [1]. In addition, 3-D braiding is one of the very few textile processes which lend themselves to the fabrication of fully integrated, net-shape preforms.

While 3-D braiding has proven very promising in enhancing the damage tolerance of polymer matrix composites where delamination is the major life-limiting failure mechanism [2], it is also of merit in metal matrix composites where the primary problem is not delamination but embrittlement resulting from the strongly bonded, brittle fibers. Preliminary results obtained on 3-D braided alumina fiber FP/Al-Li composites with a fiber volume fraction of 0.17 were encouraging [3-6]. The braided composite

showed in-plane strengths and stiffnesses comparable to those of 2-D laminated composites while offering a greater resistance to crack propagation under static and dynamic loading conditions. 3-D braiding of fibers also resulted in a small improvement in the friction and wear resistance of the FP/Al-Li composites [7].

This paper presents recent progress in the characterization of 3-D braided FP/AL-Li composites including data on the effect of fiber content. In addition to the studies reported here, the biaxial loading (combined torsion and tension) response of the braided composite is also being investigated and the results will be reported elsewhere.

MATERIAL

3-D braided, $\pm 20^\circ$ angle-ply, and unidirectional composites used in this study were all vacuum melt infiltrated by DuPont Company. The properties of fiber FP and the AL-Li matrix alloy are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1
Properties of Constituent Materials

<u>Fiber FP</u>	
Tensile Modulus	345-379 GPa
Tensile Strength	1.4 GPa
Elongation	0.4%
Diameter	20 microns
<u>Al-2.5 pct Li</u>	
Tensile Modulus	73 GPa
Tensile Strength	154 MPa
Yield Strength	83 MPa
Elongation	11%

3-D preforms were braided at Drexel University by Dr. Frank Ko. These had an average surface braid angle of 20° and a bundle size consisting of 10 yarns (approx. 2,500 fibers). The braided composites had two fiber volume fractions: 0.17 and 0.34. It must be noted, however, that the integrated nature of the 3-D braided construction necessitates a synergism

among the fiber orientation, fiber volume fraction, and bundle size. Therefore, some variation between the braid angle of composites with the two fiber volume fractions is to be expected. In addition, since each specimen was braided separately to its net shape and required a particular loom design determined by its dimensions, even within each V_f group, some variation existed in the fiber volume fraction of specimens with different dimensions.

All specimens were inspected by ultrasonic C-scan technique prior to mechanical testing.

Test Procedures

All specimens were tested in the as-cast condition and at room temperature. Specimen configurations and test procedures for tension, compression, and shear tests have been described in references 3 and 4.

Fracture toughness was measured on compact tension and straight-notched three-point bend specimens. Details of the compact tension tests have been given elsewhere [5]. The bend specimens were 6.3mm x 6.3mm x 76mm for the braided composites and 12.7mm x 12.7mm x 76mm for the angle-ply laminates and had crack length/depth ratios in the range of approximately 0.3 to 0.6. The span was 51mm in both cases. The above size difference was due to the varying thicknesses of the two composite panels.

Instrumented impact tests were conducted in drop-weight towers as described previously [6] except that instead of previously used equipment, new tests on the high- V_f braided composites as well as additional tests on the low- V_f braided and the unidirectional composites were performed on two "Dynatup" drop towers: models 8200 and 8010A equipped with the GRC 730-I data acquisition system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Strength and Stiffness

Doubling the fiber volume fraction resulted in an almost two-fold increase in the strength and stiffness of the 3-D braided composites as shown in Table 2. This is indicative of the good infiltration of the composite at high V_f . The initial Young's modulus correlated well with the predictions of the "fiber inclination model" of Yang, Ma, and Chou [8].

The correlation is illustrated in Figure 1 for the axial Young's modulus.

The axial strength and stiffness of braided composites appear to fall between those of unidirectional and $\pm 20^\circ$ angle-ply laminates (Figure 2). Figure 3 illustrates the axial tensile stress-strain curves for the composites and the unreinforced matrix. A possible reason for the higher strength and stiffness of the braided composite over that of the angle-ply laminate, if such a difference really exists, could be the local alignment of fiber yarns along the 0° direction as they change orientation within the braid. This may also account for the lower elongation of the braided composite.

The failure mechanisms of high- V_f braided composites were similar to those of low- V_f composites described previously [1,2].

Impact Behavior

Load-time traces for the braided and unidirectional composites at various energy levels are shown in Figure 4. The maximum load and the initial stiffness reflect the contribution of fibers and are highest for the unidirectional composite. All three composites demonstrated almost identical extent of damage at 6.75 joule impact energy. Damage initiated as a tensile crack perpendicular to the fibers. For perforation, specimens were impacted with approximately 600 joule energy.

Table 3 shows the impact energies absorbed by the composites and the unreinforced matrix alloy. E_I is the energy absorbed up to the maximum load, E_p is that during the falling portion of the load-deflection curve, and E_T is the total absorbed energy. 3-D braiding clearly improves the energy absorption capacity of the FP/AL-Li composites. Among the possible reasons is fiber bunching in the microstructure of the braided composite which promotes matrix plastic deformation and fiber bundle debonding and pullout. In the unidirectional composite, the crack, once initiated, runs rapidly across the specimen width and through its thickness while in the braided composite the matrix rich areas between the fiber bundles serve as crack arresters and slow down the crack propagation. A schematic illustration of this is shown in Figure 5.

The above line of reasoning, however, cannot explain the effect of fiber content on the toughness of the braided composite. The effect is indeed somewhat paradoxical: the energy absorption capacity increases with

TABLE 2
Mechanical Properties of 3-D Braided FP/Al-Li Composites
as a Function of Fiber Volume Fraction

Property	Fiber Volume Fraction	
	0.17	0.36
Axial Tension		
Ultimate Strength (MPa)	189	383
Young's Modulus (GPa)	97	171
Poisson's Ratio	0.30	0.27
Axial Compression		
Ultimate Strength (MPa)	837.6	1524
Young's Modulus (GPa)	106	169
Poisson's Ratio	0.30	0.26

Fig. 1. Comparison of the experimental axial tensile Young's modulus with theoretical predictions[8]. (•) experiment, (—) theory.

Fig. 2. The axial tensile strength of FP/Al-Li composites as a function of the fiber content.

Fig. 3. Axial tensile stress-strain responses of FP/Al-Li composites and the unreinforced matrix.

Fig. 4. Load-time responses of FP/Al-Li composites at various impact energies.

TABLE 3

Instrumented Drop-Weight Impact Data for Perforation Tests

Material	Impact Energy, J	Velocity, m/s	Absorbed Energy, J		
			E_I	E_P	E_T
3-D Braided FP/Al-Li					
$V_f = 0.17$	618 *	4.0	52	111	163
	292 *	3.6	68	196	264
$V_f = 0.36$	618	4.0	100	160	255
Unidirectional FP/Al-Li					
$V_f = 0.34$	618	4.0	62	79	141
Al-Li Alloy	614 *	5.3	173	145	318

* Data obtained previously [6] with a different impact equipment and data acquisition system.

increasing fiber content while at the same time the composite fails in a more brittle manner. Despite its considerably higher absorbed energy, the braided composite failed in a manner similar to that of the unidirectional laminate, exhibiting both radial and circumferential cracks [6]. At the fiber content of 0.17, the behavior was close to that of the unreinforced matrix.

Fracture Toughness

Fracture toughness data from compact tension tests and notched three-point bend beam tests for 3-D braided, $\pm 20^\circ$ angle-ply, and unidirectional composites are given in Table 4. K_{IC}^L is the fracture toughness for crack running perpendicular to fibers or the major reinforcement axis and K_{IC}^T is that for the parallel crack propagation.

Similar to the impact test results, the fracture toughness of the braided composite increases with increasing fiber content and is higher than that of either unidirectional or angle-ply laminates. For all three composites, K_{IC}^L is larger than K_{IC}^T which follows the strength data.

It is not quite clear why fracture toughnesses obtained from bend tests are smaller than those from compact tension tests except that in the case of the braided composite the two specimens had somewhat different fiber volume fractions for the reason explained earlier.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is supported by the Office of Naval Research. Dr. L. H. Peebles, Jr., is the project manager.

Experiments on the braided composites with high fiber content were performed by Mr. Olivier G. Remond.

Fig. 5. Schematic illustration of crack propagation through the thickness of the unidirectional and 3-D braided FP/Al-Li composites during impact at 54 J.

TABLE 4

Fracture Toughness Data for FP/Al-Li Composites
Fracture Toughness, $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$

Material	Three-Point Bend Test		Compact Tension Test	
	K_{IC}^L	K_{IC}^T	K_{IC}^L	K_{IC}^T
3-D Braided $V_f = 0.17$	-	-	24.9	17.4
$V_f = 0.36$	21.7	-	32.3	21.2
$\pm 20^\circ$ Angle-Ply $V_f = 0.34$	17.4	9.4	-	-
Unidirectional $V_f = 0.34$	-	-	31.7	15-17*

* Richter [11].